

Modelling and Forecasting Stock Market Trend Using Markov Chain Process: A Study of Dar Es Salam Stock Exchange, Tanzania

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ABSTRACT:

This study applies a Markov Chain model to forecast the behaviour of the Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) market. DSE serves as the only official platform for share trading in Tanzania. The application of the Markov Chain model in forecasting future states relies on the inherent randomness exhibited by the DSE market. This study utilizes the Markov Chain model to forecast future conditions based on the inherent randomness observed in the DSE market. It aims to explore the long-term dynamics of the market, estimate how often specific states are revisited, and calculate the expected time for the market to return to those states. The analysis utilizes secondary data from 1,847 trading days of DSE index values, covering the period from August 25, 2014, to November 18, 2021, sourced from the DSE office.

The study reveals that in the long run, regardless of the current state of the DSE market, share prices are most likely to remain stable, with a probability of approximately 91%, while the chances of depreciation and appreciation are relatively low, at around 5% and 4%, respectively. This indicates a relatively steady market environment with minimal and predictable price movements, reflecting low long-term volatility. Such stability may appeal to long-term, risk-averse investors, but it also highlights limited opportunities for short-term speculative gains. The findings underscore the need to enhance market activity and liquidity by encouraging more company listings, increasing public awareness, and improving market infrastructure. These efforts could help develop a more vibrant and responsive stock market, thereby strengthening the DSE's role in supporting broader economic development.

Keywords: Markov Chain Process, DSE market, Stock returns, Stock Forecasting, Tanzania.

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INTRODUCTION

The stock market serves as the venue for the transfer, trading, and circulation of issued stocks. It is an organized platform where buyers and sellers come together to trade shares of publicly listed companies. Due to its strong connection with the social economy, it is often referred to as the measure of economic and financial activities in the country [1,2]. The stock exchange can be categorized into primary and secondary markets. In primary markets, entities such as corporations, governments, municipalities, and other incorporated organizations have the opportunity to raise capital by directing investors' savings into productive initiatives. Conversely, secondary markets involve the buying and selling of existing securities among investors or traders, typically occurring

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on a securities exchange, over-the-counter, or in other venues [3]. The stock market plays a crucial role in the rapid expansion of the global economy such that any variations in the market can greatly affect both individuals and the economy as a whole. In terms of capital accumulation and financial growth, the stock market serves as an excellent option for numerous businesses and corporations seeking to expand or establish new ventures. In a developing economy, the stock market is crucial to the framework of various business sectors represented by corporations, as it facilitates the acquisition of funds and the formation of capital for these enterprises [4].

Stocks generally signify ownership of shares in a corporation or any legal entity, providing investors with a claim on a portion of the company's assets and earnings. This ownership stake can lead to potential dividends and capital appreciation, making stock investments attractive for wealth-building over time. Moreover, stock ownership offers investors a unique opportunity to participate in the growth and success of companies they believe in, aligning their financial interests with those of the businesses. Share prices appreciate, depreciate or remain the same over a period determined by various factors such as Wrong market trend Information, Participation of the sector, Business Situations and Government Policy [5]. The shares that a company issues to its shareholders are referred to as outstanding shares. The overall value of a company's outstanding shares is termed its market capitalization, which varies according to the prevailing stock price and the quantity of shares issued. Market capitalization increases or decreases by the current market price of the shares, thereby indicating the value that the market assigns to the company [6].

Background of Stock Exchange Markets

Historically, the roots of stock exchange markets started in the ancient societies where the exchange of commodities and goods took place. For example, in 2000 BCE, traders in Mesopotamia participated in primitive forms of lending and credit. By the 12th century, traders in Europe began dealing in government bonds, setting the stage for structured financial markets. In Bruges, Belgium, brokers engaged in the trading of commercial notes and government obligations [7]. In the 16th Century, the Amsterdam Stock Exchange, founded in 1602 by the Dutch East India Company to enable the trading of its shares. With its expansion throughout Europe, other stock exchanges quickly emerged, including the London Stock Exchange (LSE) in 1801, which significantly contributed during the Industrial Revolution by providing capital for sectors such as railways, mining, and shipping. This started with the Buttonwood Agreement, signed by 24 brokers to control the trading of securities. With the NYSE and other exchanges like NASDAQ promoting technical innovation and international money flows, the United States emerged as the global financial centre by the 20th Century [8].

Internationally, following technological advancement in the late 20th century and the adoption of electronic trading, increasing gradually replaced traditional trading systems. This resulted in an automated securities trading system that was pioneered by Exchanges like NASDAQ, launched in 1971 [9]. The Major stock exchanges that exist now globally, including the Tokyo Stock Exchange (Japan), Shanghai Stock Exchange (China), and Bombay Stock Exchange (India), are the results of these developments. This enabled cross-border investments and, hence, a significant increase in international financial transactions that enhanced the efficiency of global financial markets. Conversely, these markets are also vulnerable to external risks and uncertainties stemming from the integration of the global economy facilitated by technology [10].

Globally, investors closely monitor the changes in market indices and consistently exhibit a strong interest in forecasting trends within the share market. Investors typically seek to understand the background and historical performance of publicly traded equities to aid in their investment decision-making processes. Grasping and forecasting stock market trends is essential for the purpose of making well-informed investment choices [11]. Stock market predictions are centered on formulating effective methods for anticipating index values or stock prices. The primary objective is to achieve substantial profits through clearly defined trading strategies [12]. Stock market indices and prices exhibit considerable fluctuations, often rising and falling or remaining stationary in an unpredictable manner the situations that influence investor's confidence.

Consequently, within the context of randomness it is crucial to identify more effective methods for predicting stock market indices and prices so as to enable investors to make more informed and

accurate investment decisions. In the field of stochastic analysis with discrete and randomness, a Markov chain model is used to describe a framework for the transitions of an entity between various states [13]. By characterizing these transitions as random processes, the theory of Markov dependency underscores that the subsequent state (whether the next step or position) of any process is solely determined by its present state, rather than by the historical sequence of events that have occurred over time [14]. Accordingly, finite Markov chains are suitable for modelling such processes, Markov chains provide a valuable framework for analysing sequential data, such as stock prices, by allowing a stochastic process to transition from one state to another based on probabilities [15].

Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) Profile

The Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) is the only stock exchange in Tanzania, located in Dar es Salaam, the country's largest and commercial capital city. The Exchange was incorporated on September 19, 1996, as a private company limited by guarantee, operating as a non-profit entity under the Capital Markets and Securities Act (CMSA) of 1994 [16-18].

The primary objective of the DSE was to provide a platform for companies to raise capital while offering a regulated environment for investors to trade securities. The operations of the Exchange officially began on April 15, 1998, with Tanzania Oxygen Limited (TOL) being the first company to list, followed later in the same year by Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) [16,19-21].

The establishment of the DSE also supported the Tanzanian government's initiative to privatize underperforming parastatal entities, a move aimed at boosting economic growth and reducing the fiscal burden of managing such entities. The activities of the DSE are monitored and supervised by the Capital Markets and Securities Authority (CMSA) [22]. The DSE transitioned from a mutual entity to a public limited company through demutualization, officially changing its name to Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) Public Limited Company on June 29, 2015 (PRESS RELEASE, 2015). It began share trading on May 16, 2016, becoming Africa's third self-listed exchange after Johannesburg (2006) and Nairobi (2014) [23]. Operating through the Main Investment Market Segment (MIMS) and the Enterprises Growth Market (EGM), the DSE plays a key role in Tanzania's financial sector, facilitating the trading of securities [3]. In 2021, the DSE launched Soko la Hisa Kiganjani, a mobile platform enabling nationwide securities trading, boosting market participation and liquidity, and supporting economic growth [17].

DSE is affiliated with the African Stock Exchanges Association [20] and actively participates in various international organizations, including the World Federation of Exchanges (WFE), the United Nations Sustainable Stock Exchanges (UN-SSE), the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the United Nations Global Compact, the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP-FI), and the United Nations Principles for Responsible Investment (UN-PRI). The objective is to capitalize on shared experiences and expertise among global industry leaders. Operationally, the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) collaborates closely with the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE) in Kenya and the Uganda Securities Exchange (USE) in Uganda [17,24].

Extensive research has been conducted globally to predict stock market trends in both developed and developing economies using various methodologies, including neural networks, data mining, moving averages, regression analysis, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models [12], time series analysis, and Markov Chain analysis. These studies highlight that stock market performance is influenced by multiple factors such as market dynamics, stock fundamentals, macroeconomic policies, investor psychology, global business trends, natural disasters, political and economic conditions, corporate governance, and regulatory policies [12,21,24-28].

Most existing studies focus on modeling financial time series in developed markets like the United States, China, and the United Kingdom. However, there is a noticeable gap in empirical research on stock market prediction in emerging economies, including the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) in Tanzania. Despite this, emerging markets hold substantial potential, attracting increasing interest from local and international investors [10,12].

The stochastic nature of stock markets results in random fluctuations in share prices, making forecasting complex. Understanding and predicting stock trends in emerging markets is crucial for researchers, financial analysts, investors, and regulators in making informed decisions using appropriate statistical models [29]. Considering the critical role of the stock market in promoting economic growth and facilitating investment opportunities, ongoing analysis and modeling of DSE performance trends is essential for informed decision-making and market development.

While several studies have employed the Markov Chain approach to analyse stock markets, most focus on developed economies, with limited research on the DSE. Existing studies on the DSE primarily examine price volatility, exchange and interest rates, using models such as GARCH, EGARCH, and time series analysis [13,21,28,30-33]. Some research has applied the Markov Chain model, but with different objectives, leaving a gap in forecasting stock price trends within the DSE.

This study, therefore, aims to analyse and predict stock price trends within the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange using Markov Chain analysis. Specifically, it seeks to (1) examine the trend of share prices on the DSE, (2) develop a Markov model for forecasting share prices, and (3) project future share price movements within the exchange.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Since this study focuses on the application of Markov Chain theory to stock price movements in Tanzania, it is fundamentally rooted in probability theory and stochastic processes, with particular emphasis on Markov Chain Theory. Central to this theory is the Markov property, which asserts that the future state of a system depends solely on its current state, independent of the sequence of events that preceded it [34]. In the context of financial markets, this implies that the probability of a shift in stock prices, whether an increase, decrease, or stability state, can be determined based solely on the current state, without the need to consider the full history of past trends [13,14,25].

In assessing market conditions and regulatory changes across different states, the Markov Chain model is a valuable approach for addressing time series issues, regardless of the dataset's linearity. Introduced by the Russian mathematician Andrei Andreevich Markov (1856–1922), the Markov Chain model has become particularly useful in predicting stock market behaviours [35]. According to [36], the Markov Chain model provides more accurate stock price forecasts compared to traditional trend forecasting methods, as it accounts for daily price changes to determine the states of the chain.

In alignment with this approach, the study also adopts the Efficient Market Theory (EMT), originally proposed by [37], which posits that stock prices cannot be reliably predicted using historical data, present trends, or any publicly available financial information. This theory aligns with the random walk hypothesis, which suggests that price changes occur unpredictably, with each new movement representing a random deviation from previous prices. Similarly, [38] supports the view that stock prices incorporate all available information, aligning with the principles of the Efficient Market Hypothesis. Furthermore, the applicability of this theory to African financial markets has been reinforced by empirical evidence from [39] as well as [40].

Empirical Review

Numerous studies have investigated the use of Markov Chain models for analysing and forecasting stock market trends. [41] analysed price fluctuations in the DSE in Tanzania using a Markov chain model to understand the stochastic behaviour of stock prices and provide insights into the applicability of Markov processes in modelling stock market dynamics. The study identified three levels or states of price movements, namely unchanged price, gain in price, or loss in price to the current pricing. The findings of this study indicated that, when utilizing the steady state vector (0.5177, 0.2003), there was a price decrease approximately 52% of the time.

The study by [5] applied the Markov Chain model to analyse and forecast stock price movements in three possible directions: an increase, a decrease, or no change. Their analysis focused on two major Nigerian banks, namely Guarantee Trust Bank and First Bank of Nigeria, over the period from

2005 to 2010. The findings showed that in the long run, regardless of a bank's current share price, a downward movement in price is the most expected outcome, followed by an upward movement, while a stable price is the least expected. This suggests a general tendency for price fluctuations rather than long-term stability in share values. In a related study, [12] modelled the volatility of daily stock returns on the Nairobi Stock Exchange (NSE) using a Markov Chain approach. Their analysis, based on data spanning from April 2008 to April 2012, focused on the daily closing prices of Safaricom shares. The results indicated that the share price exhibited alternating bullish and bearish trends, with an initial sideways movement reflecting price volatility. The study concluded that the estimated initial state vector and transition matrix could effectively predict the future states of Safaricom's share price movements.

The study by [42] sought to forecast the index's long-term pattern, determine how frequently each state is visited, and compute the average time it takes to revert to a specific state using secondary data from the NEPSE office covering 2,741 trading days. The findings revealed that, over the long term, the NEPSE index is most likely to experience a decline, followed by an increase, while periods of stability are the least expected. Furthermore, the study observed that once the index enters an increasing trend, it typically continues to rise for approximately three consecutive days before shifting to another state. [42], on the other hand, employed a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) for stock price analysis and prediction, focusing on the influence of Sensex movements on the share price of HDFC Bank. By examining the model parameters, an upward trend in Sensex closing values positively influenced HDFC Bank's stock performance, highlighting a strong correlation between market index performance and individual stock behaviour.

[43] utilized Markov Chain models to identify the top-performing financial stocks on the Ghana Stock Exchange for investment and portfolio construction between 2017 and 2020. They applied a Markov chain model with three distinct states to analyse how stock prices shift over time, including estimating the likelihood of transitioning between states, the steady-state probabilities, and the average duration before returning to a given state. The long-term behaviour of stock prices suggested that the steady state was the most probable. Additionally, the analysis highlighted that Standard Chartered Bank, GCB, Ecobank, and Cal Bank emerged as the best-performing stocks according to their average return intervals and equilibrium state patterns. A research study conducted by [4] in India aimed at forecasting and analysing the stock market trends of Nifty bank shares traded on the Indian Stock Exchange (ISE) through the application of a Markov chain model. The findings from the Transition Probability Matrix (TPM) reveal that if the closing price of Nifty bank is increasing, the chance for Nifty bank share prices will increase with maximum probability. The results also reveal that the average time for the market to return to a decreasing state is about 2 days, with a similar return time observed for an increasing state.

[40] analyses share price movements in the Nigerian stock market from 1985 to 2019 using the Markov chain approach, which effectively captures the time-dependent behaviour of stock prices. The model estimates the expected duration of upward and downward trends and identifies long-term probabilities that are independent of initial conditions. Results show a consistent rise in monthly share prices over time, linked to increased market activity. The study further suggests that share price dynamics impact economic performance. To boost market efficiency and investor confidence, policies should focus on limiting arbitrage, protecting investor rights, discouraging insider trading, and educating local investors.

[44] explore the application of Markov Chain modelling to the Swedish stock index OMXS30 in two distinct phases. The first phase involves constructing a Markov chain utilizing index data from recent years, while the second phase assesses the predictive capabilities of the Markov model. The initial analysis indicates a positive long-term trend for OMXS30, whereas the subsequent analysis demonstrates that a Markov model comprising six states achieves a prediction accuracy marginally exceeding that of random chance.

[45] adopted the Markov Chain model to conduct a study for comparing the performance of five prominent stocks in the Oil and Gas Sector in India by analysing the past three years' data of the sector. In the findings, it was revealed that the price four petroleum companies indicated a high probability of increase in its value while two oil companies value exhibits a higher chance of being

stable with no significant increase or decrease [45]. The study aimed to analyse the closing price of the major stockholders in the Oil and Gas sector to find which among them has better future features [45].

[11] analysed stock market behaviour using daily closing prices, focusing on stocks indexed within the NIFTY 50 in an Indian stock market. They employed the Markov Chain Model over a period covering December 2022 to December 2024, forming a 493-day trading data panel. The results demonstrated high accuracy in predicting the dynamic behaviour of the Nifty 50 index, highlighting its practical applicability in financial forecasting. Additionally, an analysis of Nifty 50 daily closing prices using a 5-day moving average graph offered deeper insights into market behaviour, and the results revealed alternating bullish and bearish trends, reflecting the market's inherent volatility and dynamism. However, despite short-term fluctuations, the overall pattern suggested a clear upward trajectory, indicating sustained growth in the Nifty 50 over time.

While similar studies using the Markov Chain approach, such as [41], have been conducted, the Tanzanian stock market has undergone significant changes since then. These include the introduction of new policies, advancements in technological infrastructure, and a rise in investor participation, all of which may have influenced share price behaviour and market dynamics. Analysing more recent data provides a timely and relevant perspective on the current state of the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), offering a clearer view of contemporary trends, volatility, and market transitions. By applying the Markov Chain model to this updated dataset, this study not only revisits previous findings in light of these changes but also deepens the understanding of both short- and long-term stock price behaviour in today's Tanzanian financial landscape, making the analysis more relevant for current investors, policymakers, and researchers. Although literature on the application of Markov Chain models in the DSE is limited, the methodologies and insights from similar studies can offer valuable guidance for analysing and predicting stock market trends within the DSE context.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Model Development

To model the dynamic behaviour of share price movements on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), a discrete-time Markov Chain model was developed. The model assumes that the future state of share prices depends only on the current state and not on the sequence of events that preceded it, satisfying the Markov property. Various researchers have explored numerous methods in this context. However, the memoryless characteristic of the Markov process appears to be particularly pertinent when analysing stock market prices for future predictions [45].

Markov Chain Process

Markov Chain processes were pioneered by Markov in 1907, also known as a founder of the stochastic theories/processes. A Markov Chain, which uses the theory of conditional probability, is a special kind of stochastic process whose state space is discrete [46].

Markov Chain is the sequence of random variables $X_0, X_1, X_2, \dots \in S$, where $S = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $X = \{X_n: n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and satisfy the Markov property:

$$P(X_n = j | X_m = i, X_{m-1} = i_{m-1}, \dots, X_0 = i_0) = P(X_n = j | X_m = i) \quad (1)$$

For all states $i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{m-1}, i_{m-2}, i, j \in S$ and $n > m$.

This means that, given the current state, the future is independent of the past.

Transition Probability

The conditional probabilities on the right-hand side of equation (1) are fundamental to describing a Markov Chain in a time-homogeneous whereas the transition probabilities remain constant over time.

These probabilities, known as transition probabilities, mean that the probability of transitioning from state i to state j is independent of the time step n and remains the same throughout the process. The transition probability from state i to state j in single step is represented as:

$$P(X_n = j | X_m = i) = P_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where P_{ij} is the entry in the i^{th} row and j^{th} column.

Transition Matrix

The subsequent step, following the identification of the state space, involves fitting the data into the model through the creation of a Transition Probability Matrix (TPM). Before conducting an additional Markov analysis of the n states in discrete time, we first established a $n \times n$ transition matrix, which is detailed in eq. (3). Each entry R_{ij} denotes the frequency of transitions from state i to state j at a given time t , $i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. For example, R_{00} specifies the count of transitions occurring from state 0 to state 0, and R_{21} denotes the count of transitions from state 2 to state 1 within a designated time frame, among other details.

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} R_{00} & R_{01} & R_{02} & \dots & R_{0n} \\ R_{10} & R_{11} & R_{12} & \dots & R_{1n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ R_{n0} & R_{n1} & R_{n2} & \dots & R_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Transition probability Matrix (TPM)

The transition matrix shown in eq. (3) serves as the foundation for constructing the Transition Probability Matrix (TPM), which consists of entries representing transition probabilities. This TPM serves as the foundation for Markov analysis. Following this, we utilize maximum likelihood estimators to derive the most accurate estimate.

P_{ij} is achieved by dividing each element in a specific row by the overall sum of all elements within that row (see equation 4) and the resulting TPM \hat{P}_{ij} :

$$\hat{p}_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij}}{R_j}, \text{ where } R_j = \sum_{i=1}^n R_{ij} \quad (4)$$

The Transition Probability Matrix (TPM) represents the likelihood of movement from one state to another, capturing short-term transitions in the system. The elements along the main diagonal of the TPM indicate the probability of remaining in the same state over a short period.

These probabilities form a $n \times n$ transition matrix P where:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{00} & P_{01} & P_{02} & \dots & P_{0n} \\ P_{10} & P_{11} & P_{12} & \dots & P_{1n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ P_{n0} & P_{n1} & P_{n2} & \dots & P_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

which satisfies the following properties:

- i. $p_{ij} \geq 0$,
- ii. $\sum_{j=1}^n p_{ij} = 1$ for all i, j and $n > m$ (6)
- iii. P_{ii} the diagonal elements indicating transition from state i to state i . [47].

Additionally, when considering transitions between states at non-consecutive trials, the probability of moving from state i at the m th trial to state j at the n th trial is called the n -step transition probability, denoted as:

$$P_{ij}^{(n)} = P(X_{m+n} = j | X_m = i) \quad (7)$$

The distribution of a Markov Chain is fully determined once equation (2) and the initial probability distribution x_0 is specified [46].

Steady-state probability- stationary probability distribution

Transition probabilities determine how state probabilities evolve. Given an initial state distribution, future state probabilities are obtained by multiplying it with the transition probability matrix. The convergence of TPM to its steady state after a long period is called ergodicity, and thus, the ergodic distribution refers to the limiting or stationary probability distribution of a dynamic system having unique steady state vectors regardless of the initial condition [44]. Further, we note that a regular Markov chain with a finite state space will settle down to its unique stationary distribution (i.e., steady state) in the long run. Meaning that after a long period n , the $(P)^n$ will have identical rows, indicating that the probability of being in any particular state no longer depends on the starting state.

Therefore, if P is a transition probability matrix representing a finite-state Markov chain that is aperiodic and irreducible (i.e., an ergodic Markov chain), then:

$$\pi = \pi P$$

$$\pi_j = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{ij}^n \quad (8)$$

Subject to the condition: $\sum_i \pi_i = 1$, with $0 \leq \pi_i \leq 1$ to obtain a unique stationary distribution each of these rows gives the steady-state probabilities and is given by a vector $\pi = \pi_1, \pi_2, \pi_3, \dots, \pi_n$.

Determination of the states

The closing share prices of the Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), when considered as distinct time units for each closing day, were categorized into a finite number of states based on percentage changes: Share price decreases (D), share prices remains steady (S), and share price increases (I). The subsequent step, following the identification of the state space, involves fitting the data into the model through the creation of a Transition Probability Matrix (TPM). Before conducting an additional Markov analysis of the three states in discrete time, we first established a 3 x 3 transition matrix, detailed in eq. 3. Each entry R_{ij} denotes the frequency of transitions from state i to state j at a given time t , $i, j = D, S, I$. For example, R_{SS} specify the count of transitions occurring from state S to state S , and R_{DI} denotes the count of transitions from state D to state I within a designated timeframe, among other details.

Assumptions of the Markov Chain Model

For a Markov Chain with a finite state space, the following assumptions must hold:

1. Markov Property means the probability of transitioning to the next state depends only on the current state, not the past [44].

$$\text{i.e., } P(X_n = j | X_m = i, X_{m-1} = i_{m-1}, \dots, X_0 = i_0) = P(X_n = j | X_m = i).$$

2. Finite State Space means the system has limited possible states.

$S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ where n is the finite number.

3. The total probability of moving from a state to all possible states equals 1.

$$\text{i.e., } \sum_{j=1}^n P_{ij} = 1, \forall i$$

4. The probability of moving from one state to another must be non-negative.

$$\text{i.e., } 0 \leq P_{ij} \leq 1 \forall i, j$$

5. The process starts with an initial distribution over the finite states.

$$\text{i.e., } P(X_0 = i) = \pi_i, \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i = 1$$

Data Source

This study employs a quantitative research approach to model and forecast stock market trends using a Markov Chain Process. The research is based on historical stock price data from the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), focusing on the transition probabilities of stock price movements over time. To achieve the study objective, this study uses secondary data collected from the daily list published by the DSE from 2014 to 2021. The time frame of the dataset (2014–2021) was determined by its availability, which limits our ability to conduct a more detailed micro-level analysis. As a result, the study focuses on modelling the stochastic process of share price movements at a broader level rather than examining the individual movements of firms listed on the second market of the Tanzanian stock exchange. The transition from one state to another, that is, the share price trend (such as a price decrease followed by another decrease or a decrease followed by steady or a decrease followed by an increase) was analysed based on the data collected [12]. The transitions were observed over eight years, providing insight into the dynamic behaviour of share prices.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Daily Trading Stock Prices Recorded on the DSE

Figure 1. A 50-Day Moving Average Trend of Daily Closing Prices on the DSE
Source: Researcher's compilation (2025).

The overall trend at the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), as depicted in Figure 1 by the moving average, indicates a prolonged and steady decline in market performance, characteristic of a bearish phase. By filtering out short-term fluctuations and market noise, the moving average highlights a

consistent downward movement in stock prices, pointing to declining investor confidence. This negative sentiment is likely influenced by domestic economic challenges such as inflation, sluggish sectoral growth, and potentially tighter monetary policies, which may have shifted investor preference toward safer assets like government securities. The persistent nature of the decline suggests sustained market weakness and limited enthusiasm from both local and international investors. Without significant economic improvements, stronger corporate earnings, or renewed market participation, the moving average trend underscores a cautious and risk-averse investment climate within the DSE.

Determination of Transition Matrix

The transition matrix shown in eq.3 serves as the foundation for constructing the Transition Probability Matrix (TPM), which consists of entries representing transition probabilities. This TPM serves as the foundation for Markov analysis. Subsequently, we applied maximum likelihood estimation to obtain the most precise estimate. P_{ij} is achieved by dividing each element in a specific row by the overall sum of all elements within that row (see equation 4), and the resulting TPM \hat{P}_{ij} (was given in eq. 5).

Table 1. Transition Matrix from 2014 - 2021

From/To	Price decrease(D)	Price remains stable(S)	Price increase(I)
Price decrease (D)	3	52	34
Price remains stable(S)	61	1573	44
Price increase(I)	25	54	1

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025)

Determination of Transition Probability Matrix (TPM)

The TPM indicates the movement from one particular state to any other state and also refers to a short-run transition. Each element on the main diagonal of the TPM represents the short-term persistence of the market in a given state. A diagonal value close to 1 indicates high persistence, meaning the market is likely to remain in that state (e.g., staying in a bull market once it enters one). Conversely, a diagonal value significantly below 0.5 suggests low persistence, implying that the market tends to transition quickly to other states. Thus, P_{DD} , P_{SS} and P_{II} , reflect the probabilities of the market remaining in the decreasing, stable, and increasing states respectively over the short term.

On the other hand, the off-diagonal elements of the TPM indicate the probability of moving from one state to another [48]. Specifically, P_{DS} and P_{DI} represent the probabilities of moving from the decrease state to the stable and increase state, respectively [48]. Similarly, P_{SD} and P_{SI} reflect the probabilities of moving from the stable state to the decrease and increase states, respectively [48]. Lastly, P_{ID} and P_{IS} indicate the probabilities of moving from the increase state to the decrease and stable states, respectively [48]. Subject to the condition that the sum of each row probabilities adds up to unity, written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{DD} + P_{DS} + P_{DI} &= 1 \\
 P_{SD} + P_{SS} + P_{SI} &= 1 \\
 P_{ID} + P_{IS} + P_{II} &= 1
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

Table 2. Transition Probabilities Matrix from 2014 - 2021

From/To	Price decrease(D)	Price remains stable (S)	Price increase(I)
Price decrease(D)	0.0337	0.5843	0.3820
Price remains stable (S)	0.0364	0.9374	0.0262
Price increase(I)	0.3125	0.6750	0.0125

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025)

The diagonal elements in TPM reported in Table 2 indicate a short-run transition for the period (2014-2021). The diagonal elements results suggest that the decrease (3.4%) and increase (1.3%) states have low persistence, meaning the market is unlikely to stay in either state for long. On the other hand, the remain the same state (93.7%) has high persistence, indicating that the market is more likely to remain stable once it enters this state. The off-diagonal elements of the transition matrix reveal key insights into market transitions. When in a decrease in share prices state, the market is most likely to move to a stable market (58.4%), suggesting that after a decline, the market tends to stabilize. There is also a moderate chance (38.2%) of transitioning to an increased state, indicating that a recovery from a downturn is possible.

When the market is in a stable state, the probability of transitioning to a decreased state is low (3.6%), implying that stability is generally maintained. The chance of moving to an increase is even lower (2.6%), suggesting that periods of stability are less likely to lead to significant price increases. Additionally, when the market is in an increased state, it is most likely to transition to a stable market (67.5%), with a moderate chance (31.3%) of shifting to a decreased state. These patterns highlight that stability plays a central role in market transitions, with the highest probabilities reflecting movements toward or from the stable state. The market does not stay in a bullish or bearish state for long, with transitioning between states being more common. However, stability itself is the most persistent state in the short run. Figure 2 provides a clear depiction of the daily stock price movements at the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange.

Figure 2. Transition diaphragm for Share Prices at the DSE from 2014-2021
 Source: Researchers' compilation (2025)

The Higher Order TPM (n –Step Transition Matrix) - Steady State Probability Distribution

We calculate the steady-state probabilities that represent the behaviour of share price after n -steps of transitions. The entries within this matrix denote the probabilities that an entity currently in a specific state will transition to another state n - steps ahead. These successive transitions were employed to assess the convergence of transition probabilities across multiple iterations n , where our model exhibits identical rows. Each row of the TPM contributes to determining the steady-state probabilities represented by the vector $\pi = (\pi_D \pi_S \pi_I)$.

As illustrated in Table 3, the TPM reaches a steady state after $n = 12$, which indicates that the Markov Chain is ergodic, allowing access to each state from any other state within a finite number of steps. Additionally, it was found that the stock market exchange is highly susceptible to external influences or fluctuations, considering the duration required for the transition to achieve a steady state. This result, therefore, leads to the establishment of steady state probabilities, which indicate the likelihood of share prices declining, remaining stable, or rising, irrespective of the most recent fluctuations in the daily closing price of the shares [12]. The iterations to the higher orders were done by use of Advanced Microsoft Excel as follows:

Table 3. The Long Run Prospect for Share Prices at the DSE from 2014-2021

P	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.03371 & 0.58427 & 0.38202 \\ 0.03635 & 0.93743 & 0.02622 \\ 0.31250 & 0.67500 & 0.01250 \end{bmatrix}$	P^2	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.14176 & 0.82527 & 0.03297 \\ 0.04350 & 0.91771 & 0.03880 \\ 0.03898 & 0.82378 & 0.13724 \end{bmatrix}$
P^6	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04894 & 0.90854 & 0.04252 \\ 0.04798 & 0.90933 & 0.0426 \\ 0.04785 & 0.90850 & 0.04365 \end{bmatrix}$	P^7	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04797 & 0.90898 & 0.04305 \\ 0.04801 & 0.90928 & 0.04271 \\ 0.04828 & 0.90907 & 0.04265 \end{bmatrix}$
P^9	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04802 & 0.90923 & 0.04275 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90926 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04805 & 0.90924 & 0.04271 \end{bmatrix}$	P^{10}	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04803 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04273 \end{bmatrix}$
P^{11}	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04273 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04803 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \end{bmatrix}$	P^{12}	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \\ 0.04802 & 0.90925 & 0.04272 \end{bmatrix}$

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025)

It can be observed from the aforementioned n -step transition matrix that, after nine (9) trading days, the probabilities begin to stabilize, indicating a tendency toward steady-state behavior. By the 12th iteration (representing the 12th closing trading day), the values in the matrix converge, signifying that the system has reached equilibrium, a point where further transitions do not significantly change the state probabilities.

Table 4. The TPM and Steady-State Vectors of DSE for the Period 2014-2021 Combined

Transition period	The Transition Probabilities Matrix (TPM)	Number of transitions to reach the steady state (n)	The steady state vectors $\pi = (\pi_D \ \pi_S \ \pi_I)$.
2014 -2021	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0337 & 0.0364 & 0.3125 \\ 0.5843 & 0.9374 & 0.6750 \\ 0.3820 & 0.0262 & 0.0125 \end{bmatrix}$	12	[0.04802 0.90925 0.04272]

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025)

The convergence of the transition matrix to a steady-state distribution indicates that the Markov chain is ergodic, which means that it is possible to reach any state from any other state [12] (i.e., the chain is irreducible), and it does not get trapped in cycles (i.e., it is aperiodic). This property ensures that, over time, the market will settle into a unique long-run equilibrium distribution, regardless of the initial state. In this context, it means the market behaviour modelled by the chain becomes predictable in the long run, with stable probabilities assigned to each state (decrease, stable, or increase). Table 4 presents the steady-state results, showing that the market is most likely to remain in a stable state (90.9%) over the long run, indicating strong stability with minimal fluctuations. The probability of staying in a bear market is low (4.8%), suggesting that downturns are typically short-lived. Likewise, the bull market shows an even lower persistence (4.3%), which implies that while the bull market is present, it is fleeting, and investors should expect stability to follow rather than a prolonged period of continued growth. Overall, the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) market is expected to remain predominantly stable in the long run, with very limited persistence in both bullish and bearish conditions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study represents a novel contribution to the literature, as it initiates critical discourse and offers new perspectives on stock market behaviour by utilizing the Markov Chain method. By investigating the nature and persistence of stock price movements on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), the study enhances the understanding of market behaviour over time. The conclusions drawn are

expected to be of substantial relevance to a broad audience, including investors, financial analysts, policymakers, regulators, and other key stakeholders within and beyond Tanzania's financial markets.

The findings revealed that once the daily closing DSE share prices enter the remain the same state (90%, they are most likely to stay stable in the short run. In contrast, the decrease and increase states exhibit greater short-run instability, with higher probabilities of transitioning to other states. Moreover, the convergence of the transition matrices to a steady-state distribution suggests ergodicity, a property commonly observed in stock markets, thereby reinforcing the model's applicability. Ultimately, in the long run, regardless of the current state of share prices, the model predicts that the DSE share prices will most likely remain stable, with a probability of approximately 91%, while the chances of depreciation and appreciation are relatively low, at around 5% and 4%, respectively.

These findings highlight the importance of enhancing market activity and liquidity through increased company listings, greater public awareness, and improved market infrastructure. Such initiatives could foster a more dynamic and responsive stock market, thereby strengthening the DSE's contribution to broader economic development. Moreover, the DSE appears to offer limited opportunities for short-term speculative trading, making it more appealing to risk-averse, long-term investors who value stability over rapid returns. Consequently, the insights from this study are valuable for policymakers, stock market regulators, investors, researchers, and other key stakeholders within and beyond Tanzania's financial markets in understanding the underlying dynamics of stock market behaviour and in formulating strategies to promote a robust and sustainable economic environment.

This study is subject to certain limitations that should be addressed in future research to strengthen the robustness and generalizability of the findings. First, future research could expand its scope by including multiple stock markets across Sub-Saharan African countries, allowing for comparative analysis and a deeper understanding of regional market dynamics. Second, conducting sector-specific analyses within individual stock markets would provide valuable insights into how different industries respond to varying market conditions. Third, incorporating key macroeconomic variables, such as inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and GDP growth, could improve the explanatory power of future models. Finally, researchers may explore time-varying or regime-switching transition probabilities to capture shifts in market behaviour during periods of economic instability or political shocks.

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